

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Report on descriptive case studies

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
Work Package	WP1
Deliverable	D1.5
Period covered	M18-M36
Publication date	31/10/2025
Dissemination level	PU
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	EVENOR
Authors	Blanco-Velázquez Francisco José, Gonzalez-Peñaloza Félix, Bravo-García Javier, Anaya-Romero María
Contributors	

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed by the NOVASOIL consortium according to the national reports and comments received

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	01/10/2025	EVENOR	Draft version online provided
2	V1.1	15/10/2025	All	Comments and suggestions were provided
3	V2.0	31/10/2025	EVENOR	Comments and improvements accepted

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

Table of contents

1	Summary	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
2	Introduction.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
2.1	Objectives.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
2.2	Potential use of the document.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
2.3	Outline the document.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3	Main sources of information.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.1	Case studies	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Integrated production in the vineyards (NBU).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Integrated production in Estonia (METK).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture- Payment for Ecosystem Services (UNIFI)	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: District of the Sands - Carbon Credits (DELTA & UNIFE).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Rueda,Organic vineyards- Integrated production.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Integrated Production in Andalusian Olive Groves (ASAJA).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas - Value chain (UNIFI).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: ZSA DIH System (ZSA).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: CO2-Land initiative in Germany (TUM).....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Tamarguillo Park.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	CS: Rabo Carbon Bank (WU)	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.2	Feasibility of new business models for practitioners.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
4	Business models	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
4.1	Business models and their features	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	Value Chain Payments.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5	Design guide: list of potential parameters and options.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.

5.1	Actors/Parties involved	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.2	Payment characteristics	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.3	Object of business model.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.4	Contracts: Findings from DCEs.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.5	Monitoring & enforcement.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.6	Sanctions.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.7	Flexibiity.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.8	Information as a part of the role	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.9	Eligibility/Conditions for participation .	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5.10.	Prioritised Soil Parameters for Monitoring;	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
6	Design guide - decision trees for innovative business model types..	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
6.1	Payment per ecosystem services.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
6.2	Carbon credits	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
6.3	Result-based.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
6.4	Value-chain.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
7.	Discussion, Conclusions and the next Steps...	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
7	Acknowledgment	43

1 Introduction

This deliverable (**D1.5 – Report on descriptive case studies**) brings together the descriptive and lessons learned of the case studies. To facilitate, it has been designed as factsheets and can be found in the project website.

2. Factsheets

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

A model for multifunctional and sustainable development of marginal areas

Summarize

Along the Emilia-Romagna coast, farming takes place on highly sandy soils that are productive yet fragile. The area faces chronic pressures: salinisation driven by sea-water intrusion and drought, subsidence linked to hydrology and land use, gradual loss of soil organic matter (SOM) and, in places, legacy contamination. The case study sets an explicit dual ambition. Agronomically, it aims to rebuild organic matter and water-holding capacity so that fields weather heat and irregular rainfall without sacrificing yield stability.

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Objectives

In the NOVASOIL Project, we will focus on learning from experiences in the project by exploring the effectiveness of the actions made in terms of soil fertility and health improvement, productivity rising, resilience and landscape valorisation. We will investigate the possibility to develop a business models aiming at adding value to the agronomic management aimed at soil health conservation with innovative crop products through certification and production standards.

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

The sandy soils in the study area are characterized by two critical issues: Salinization and salt intrusion, which lead to reduced yields; Low organic matter content.

Potential enablers

Adoption by participating companies of certifications (e.g., Organic, Integrated Production SQNPI, Globalgap and Grasp, Qualità Vivalistica Italia); Participation in innovative research projects; Sharing investments among farmers and collaboration with government bodies (public-private dialogue).

Potential stakeholders

Agricultural companies and cooperatives operating on sandy soils and participating in the PIL (Political Innovation Lab); land managers such as local authorities; specifically, the questionnaire was distributed to the departments of environment, agriculture, and land-use and cultural planning, land reclamation consortia for irrigation management, the Emilia-Romagna Po Delta Park, agricultural trade associations, and environmental associations; technicians and freelancers such as local geologists and agronomists.

Preliminary results

Early outcomes point to incremental but lasting improvements: higher soil organic carbon, stronger aggregation and infiltration, and reduced erosion, translating into more resilient yields. Economically, farms secure a predictable public support floor complemented by new revenue from credits, while confidence grows as MRV costs fall with stable sampling designs and remote-sensing integration. Institutionally, the model demonstrates how blending action-based and results-based instruments within a district framework can deliver credible certification and practical benefits on challenging sandy soils.

Economic perspective

The Sustainability District treats carbon credits as a component, not the whole story. SOM increases and reduced erosion are translated into carbon removal/emission reduction claims that can be certified and marketed; meanwhile, the same practice set underpins a product-quality and stewardship narrative that coastal buyers can recognise (labels, standards, supplier programmes). This creates two revenue streams:

1. Result-based income from verified carbon outcomes; and
2. Value-chain premia (or preferential procurement) for produce carrying the District's stewardship claim.

Importantly, the case embraces hybrid incentives. A public, action-based floor (eco-schemes/AES for cover crops, reduced tillage, landscape features) provides predictability and helps cover extra costs. On top, the result-based carbon component

Policy and governance

The Italian case highlights farmers' reluctance towards long, volatile carbon contracts and complex monitoring, showing preference for short-to-medium commitments with renewal options and per-hectare payments that reflect real costs. Policy instruments should therefore combine eco-scheme or AES-based support with seed funding to cover initial MRV and protocol design, de-risking early participation.

Governance is structured around a District Operator (co-operative, consortium, producer organisation) acting as aggregator: it standardises practices, manages data and sampling, negotiates with buyers/certifiers, operates risk buffers and distributes payments. Regional authorities and paying agencies provide action-based floors, oversee compliance, and co-finance MRV. Certification bodies validate quantification and permanence, while water and land authorities address drainage and salinity risks. Research and advisory partners contribute protocols, decision-support tools and QA/QC.

District of the Sands

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

BULGARIA

Specific objectives

- SO1** Development of a multidimensional portfolio of business cases and good practices for investments in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models worldwide to create new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Application of a co-development concept in modelling to promote soil health.
- SO4** Development of a prototype for an incentive toolbox and a test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and farmers' income security.
- SO6** Building a community of practice among investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increasing interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan.

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Germany

NOVASOIL

The NOVASOIL project aims to demonstrate the benefits of investing in soil health for society and the environment. The main outcome of the project is an instrument for assessing the suitability of different business models to promote soil health. This tool is based on best-practice examples in Europe and other countries and is tailored to the needs and requirements of the stakeholders.

“Bodenfruchtbarkeitsfonds” Summary

Soil fertility is declining due to overuse and unsustainable management of agricultural land, which increases pressure on farms and leads to soil degradation. The EU estimates humus losses at €38 billion annually.

The Soil Fertility Fund (BFF) provides financial and technical support to farmers in maintaining and improving soil fertility. With donations, the costs of fertility-enhancing measures can be compensated. This initiative aims to raise awareness of soil fertility and create broad social support for its preservation and development. In the long term, the fund contributes to strengthening soil fertility on agricultural land and to achieving climate and environmental goals. The case study illustrates the success factors and the potential for more efficient environmental programmes.

Figure 1. NOVASOIL project structure

Characteristics of the case studies

Potential inhibitors

Lack of interest/acceptance among farmers (e.g. due to restrictions in the cultivation of certain crops/incompatibility with current farming systems). Financial/return model.

Potential enabler

Societal awareness (consumers who demand high-quality and healthy food respond to environmentally friendly production), farmers who react with sustainable practices. Existing networks and associations. Political framework.

Potential stakeholders

The BFF allows consumers to become sponsors of soil fertility for the land that provides their food. A donation of €100 or 112 CHF per year supports the fertility of 2500 m² of land. Farmers and companies can also contribute to the concept through donations.

Data availability

Risks

The case operates within a dense policy environment. In Germany, GAEC minimum soil cover (enhanced CAP conditionality) and the Fertiliser Ordinance/Law (DÜV/DüngG) define the compliance baseline. Any credited outcome must exceed these standards to satisfy CRCF additionality and durability requirements. As this is also a risk for the buyers of certificates and partner institutions, CO₂-Land maintains a 20% buffer of the expected carbon storage potential across all project areas. This reserve serves to compensate for lower-than-expected soil carbon gains on certain plots or farms

Preliminary results

SOC accumulation depends strongly on environmental factors such as climate, region, and soil type, which means that humus losses due to weather or site conditions may occur. Consequently, the success of humus-building measures cannot be guaranteed. CO₂ considers this risk for participating farmers by guaranteeing that participating farmers do not face any penalties if soil organic matter levels stagnate or even decrease over time. In such cases, the only cost is incurred by soil tests. Also, to mitigate this risk, if stagnating SOC levels are detected with soil tests, potential causes are analysed

Economic perspective

The park's financing combines a basic operational layer with a results-based layer. The first ensures steady funding from the regular parks budget for routine maintenance and soil-friendly practices, providing cash flow stability. The second rewards measurable ecosystem outcomes, using transparent tariffs per unit delivered. Ecosystem-service valuation tools (e.g., i-Tree, InVEST) translate these outcomes into monetary terms, strengthening accountability and co-funding opportunities. Funding responsibility is shared: the base is covered by the parks budget, while results payments come from the departments that benefit directly, supplemented by CSR or climate funds. Multi-year agreements give financial certainty, and framework contracts plus digital monitoring reduce costs and administrative burden.

Policy and governance

The case operates within a dense policy environment. In Germany, GAEC minimum soil cover (enhanced CAP conditionality) and the Fertiliser Ordinance/Law (DÜV/DüngG) define the compliance baseline. Any credited outcome must exceed these standards to satisfy CRCF additionality and durability requirements. To monitor the development of SOC levels, soils are tested at the beginning of the contract and in the fourth and tenth year after the contract starts. In their efforts to increase SOC, participating farmers are supported with agronomic advice provided by CO₂-Land advisors.

CO₂-Land initiative in Germany

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

A model for multifunctional and sustainable development of marginal areas

Summarize

The case study derives from an integrated supply chain project funded in the framework of EU's Rural Development Policy, which involved research centres, private companies, farmers, and public administrations, to drive force of rural sustainable development through new cropping systems and management innovations. The internal and hilly areas of Tuscany Region are marginal areas characterized by conventional extensive agriculture, mainly rely on cereal crops, and little agricultural value. Soil erosion, nutrient leaching, reduction of C in soils, certainly represent the main critical issues in these areas.

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Objectives

In the NOVASOIL Project, we will focus on learning from experiences in the project by exploring the effectiveness of the actions made in terms of soil fertility and health improvement, productivity rising, resilience and landscape valorisation. We will investigate the possibility to develop a business models aiming at adding value to the agronomic management aimed at soil health conservation with innovative crop products through certification and production standards.

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

Competition with products from other countries with a lower cost,
Market changes
Extreme weather conditions (extreme rainfall, floods, and drought)

Potential enablers

Local, organic certified organic and fully traceable final products
Social awareness interested in high quality and healthy product
Existing farmer network
Higher revenue for farmers compared to previous cropping system

Potential stakeholders

Tuscany Region - Regional administration | Private companies | Farmers | Farmer association | Accademia dei Georgofili

Ecosystem services

Data availability

Risks

Signal-to-noise in SOC is addressed through multi-year sampling windows, consistent laboratories/methods and composite sampling over adequate area. Yield or weed surprises during transition are mitigated with locally adapted cover-crop mixes and carefully timed termination that protects the following cash crop, backed by accessible advisory support. Administrative load is kept lean by aligning MRV calendars with farm operations, using standard templates and accepting digital submissions. Permanence and liability are managed through rolling contracts with renewal options, programme-level buffer accounts and clauses that fairly account for uncontrollable weather shocks.

Preliminary results

At scale, the CiRAA scheme is expected to improve topsoil structure, enhance infiltration and water storage and deliver stable or rising SOC in the upper profile—while preserving commercially viable rotations and quality. The same evidence base enables cleaner contracts: realistic targets, clear baselines and proportionate checks so farmers know what is expected and agencies or buyers can defend payments.

Economic perspective

Public **action-based payments** cover additional inputs and a portion of income risk during transition. The result-based top-up then pays for maintained or improved performance relative to the baseline, with payment curves that recognise plateaus (rewarding the preservation of good status) and share uncertainty through modest buffers for inter-annual variability. Transitional grants can target first-time investments (e.g., seeders/rollers, cover-crop seed), while cooperatives lower unit costs via pooled procurement and shared machinery.

Policy and governance

The governance framework is embedded within the CAP architecture but refined to reduce administrative complexity and ensure accountability. The regional CAP paying agency defines eligibility rules, issues action-based contracts (e.g. organic management, reduced tillage, cover crops), and processes farmer claims, while a PES operator manages the result-based top-ups, establishes performance thresholds, and oversees verification. Independent research partners act as neutral knowledge brokers, providing technical protocols, QA/QC, and ensuring that indicators remain agronomically sound and proportionate. Farmers and cooperatives carry out the practices, maintain concise field logs, and co-design operational calendars for sowing, termination, and harvest, while third-party certifiers conduct light-touch audits that integrate seamlessly with paying-agency workflows. This clear division of responsibilities not only reduces duplication and transaction costs but also strengthens trust between stakeholders, particularly in the critical early phase of baseline establishment.

CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture- Payment for Ecosystem Services

The CiRAA long-term experiments (LTEs) at the University of Pisa constitute one of Italy's most valuable living laboratories for soil-health management. Running continuously since the mid-1980s across substantial field scales, the LTEs compare conservation agriculture (reduced or no tillage, cover crops) with conventional mouldboard ploughing, and juxtapose organic and conventional whole-farm systems under realistic rotations. The case study's ambition is to translate this rare continuity of biophysical and economic evidence into a Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) architecture.

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

Integrated Production Summarize

The integrated olive grove is a successful business model that promotes soil health and sustainability. It is a reliable and profitable way to produce both table olives and olive oil. The regional government provides information on modifications and pest risk forecasts to ensure the product meets environmental and social quality standards.

The NOVASOIL project aims to analyze the feasibility and characteristics of this model and replicate it in other areas or crops. The project involves a stakeholder community that includes the main players in the sector and their links to the market. The study includes 20 commercial plots with representative soils of the Mediterranean area to provide necessary information for the project's objectives

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

Economic crisis, Climate Change, competition with products from other countries with a lower cost.

Potential enablers

Social awareness (interested in high quality and healthy product)
Existing farmer network and policies.

Potential stakeholders

APICOLIVAR, ASECOL, OLEOESTEPA, OPRACOL, Regional administration, Farmer association, Oil press.

Ecosystem services

Risks

Climate variability, particularly prolonged droughts and heavy rainfall events that complicate cover crop management and soil carbon stability. There is also a risk of administrative burden for farmers, derived from certification and control requirements. Economically, fluctuations in olive oil prices can dilute the added value of IP if consumer communication is not strengthened.

Preliminary results

The system offers clear results: greater soil resilience against erosion and degradation, increases in soil organic carbon in surface horizons, reduced pest pressure through integrated pest management, and improved market image of the product. In Mediterranean soils analysed under the NOVASOIL project, the following outcomes were observed:

- Measurable increases in soil organic carbon and structural stability, mainly in the alleys.
- Reduction of erosion in sloping areas through well-managed cover crops.
- Greater efficiency in the use of inputs, with reduced mineral nitrogen applications.
- Certified products (olives and olive oil) with recognised environmental and social value.

Economic perspective

The profitability of the model is built on three pillars:

- **Controlled costs**, thanks to reduced use of external inputs and the reuse of local biomass (shredded prunings, spontaneous covers).
- **Diversified income**, through differentiated sales with the IP label, public support, and, in the future, possible market premiums linked to carbon footprint reduction or the provision of ecosystem services.
- **Cooperative scale**, which facilitates the aggregation of certified product, reduces audit costs, and consolidates the brand in international markets.

Policy and governance

The Junta de Andalucía, through its Integrated Production system, defines the technical crop standards, provides updated information on phytosanitary risks, and controls compliance through authorised bodies. The system relies on a community of stakeholders: farmers, cooperatives, mills, technical advisory companies, and certification bodies, all connected with the market.

Olives in integrated production

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Spain

Data availability

Chemical

- pH (1:5)
- E.C. (mS/cm)
- Macronutrients (N,Ca,P...)
- Micronutrients (Fe,Mb,Cu...)
- Active Calcium
- Carbonates (% CO₂)
- CEC (meq/100g)
- Heavy metals

Biological

- Organic Matter (%)
- C/N Ratio
- Organic carbon (%)
- Nematods genus
- Fungi presence

Physical

- Clay (%)
- Silt (%)
- Sand (%)
- Texture

Risks

Operational risks (reversal after heatwaves, vandalism, contamination hotspots) are managed through zoning (high-risk areas capped or phytostabilised), portfolio buffers (a share of outcomes banked to cover setbacks) and seasonal rules that keep vulnerable surfaces covered during peak heat and traffic. Price and demand risks are lower than in farm carbon markets, but budget volatility is real; the scheme therefore diversifies payers (municipal departments, utility partners, CSR sponsors) and uses multi-year service agreements to smooth flows. Administrative burden is contained by the single-window operator, standard templates and batched audits; citizen-science inputs are curated, not relied upon for compliance.

Preliminary results

The expected outcomes are tangible in an urban park. Soils gain SOM, lose compaction and hold water better; runoff and heat pressures ease as cover improves and sealed areas shrink; biodiversity returns in ground flora and invertebrates where disturbance falls. Economically, the park unlocks new value streams tied to services the city already needs; stormwater retention, cooling, safer soils, housing revaluation; while the public base keeps routine care predictable. Institutionally, Tamarguillo Park demonstrates that a hybrid PES can translate urban soil stewardship into defensible contracts with credible, lightweight MRV, offering a template other city parks can adopt and scale

Economic perspective

The park's financing combines a basic operational layer with a results-based layer. The first ensures steady funding from the regular parks budget for routine maintenance and soil-friendly practices, providing cash flow stability. The second rewards measurable ecosystem outcomes, using transparent tariffs per unit delivered. Ecosystem-service valuation tools (e.g., i-Tree, InVEST, SWMM) translate these outcomes into monetary terms, strengthening accountability and co-funding opportunities. Funding responsibility is shared: the base is covered by the parks budget, while results payments come from the departments that benefit directly, supplemented by CSR or climate funds. Multi-year agreements give financial certainty, and framework contracts plus digital monitoring reduce costs and administrative burden. Overall, the model aligns financial flows with verified environmental services, providing predictable income for park operations while incentivising performance, efficiency, and scalability across districts.

Policy and governance

Governance is kept local and simple: the municipality leads contracts and oversight, while a programme operator manages results, data, and verification. Universities ensure scientific rigour, civil society contributes to monitoring, and planning/transport departments align works with ecological goals. Transparent MRV, based on soil tests, remote sensing and open dashboards, guarantees credibility at low cost.

Payment for Ecosystem Services in the Tamarguillo Park

Business model

EPSG:4326 | 5.88,37.40
Soñic, Spain.

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

NOVASOIL
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Data availability

Risks

Drought and heat can make it hard to establish covers or force growers to end them early, so the programme leans into what works in dry years: drought tolerant mixes, flexible sowing and termination windows, and moisture saving tactics such as rolling and mulch to keep limited water in the soil. When late cold snaps arrive, spring frosts may dictate unusual ground operations; the rules reflect that reality and allow pragmatic derogations so farms do not lose eligibility for acting on seasonal needs.

Preliminary results

On Rueda's gravelly sands, gains are incremental but durable: higher SOC in the surface horizon, better aggregation/infiltration, fewer bare-soil days in windy or storm-prone windows, and more stable yields and must quality under heat. Economically, holdings stack a predictable public base with small but reliable top-ups, while saving on inputs through composted by-products and shared kit. Institutionally, the case shows how IP certification + eco-schemes + light, result-based MRV can be woven into a coherent, low-friction offer that is credible to buyers, workable for administrators and usable for growers.

Economic perspective

On the market side, swings in grape prices and the thinness of voluntary credit demand are steadied by a public payment floor, explicit cost coverage for the results layer, and, where buyers value stewardship, multi year offtake that smooths income. The action-based base comes from eco-schemes/AECM and supports the predictable cost of covers, reduced tillage and biodiversity strips; IP certification anchors market access and signals quality. On top, a result-based top-up pays for delivered outcomes: fewer bare-soil days across the risk season, SOC increases (or maintenance of good status) and demonstrably lower erosion exposure on sensitive blocks. Because wineries already generate pomace and prunings, composting/chipping reduces purchased inputs; co-op procurement and shared machinery keep unit costs down.

Policy and governance

The policy framework ensures credibility and lowers entry barriers for farmers. Under the CAP, regional authorities and paying agencies provide the basic compliance floor through eco-schemes and AECM, while co-financing baselines and MRV set-up in the initial seasons. Compliance is safeguarded by multiple regulatory bodies: Integrated Production is verified by its control authority, GAEC standards establish rules on soil cover and tillage on slopes, and nitrates regulations further define obligations in vulnerable zones.

Organic vineyards in integrated production

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism

Summarize

The aim of the Case Study in the Plovdiv region is to value the potential of local and regional traditional products in the wine sector and strengthen their relationship with communities in order to develop the local economy and agricultural sector.

The effective functioning of the wine sector in recent years leads to the improvement and stabilization of the sector as a whole, increasing the quality and competitiveness of Bulgarian wines, both in the domestic and foreign markets.

The Plovdiv region case study will focus on investigating experience in the project by focusing on different interventions for reducing soil erosion, increasing productivity, and based on landscape alliance and cooperation with other local tourism to reach added value to the agronomic management.

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Objectives

The objective is to investigate the local and regional traditional products through certification and production standards giving additional opportunities to touch with the culture and traditions of the local economy and communities. As a result, new business models can be defined, aiming to manage soil health and add value to the wine supply chain.

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

The Regional Vine and Wine Chamber (RVWC) "Trakia" – Plovdiv, Agricultural and Credit Cooperative "Solidarnost" – Plovdiv, Vineyard and wine cooperative cellar, Brestovitsa, Plovdiv region, Agricultural University – Plovdiv, Regional administration, Farmer association

Potential enablers

Economic crisis, Climate Change, competition with products from other countries with a lower cost

Potential stakeholders

Social awareness (interested in high quality and healthy product)
Existing supply chain network and policies programs/measures

Economic perspective

Revenue stems from a mix of premia and volume. First, a quality/heritage premium for bottles carrying the stewardship claim and local label; second, higher margin direct sales linked to tourism; third, where appropriate, modest public top-ups (e.g., eco-scheme style supports) to de-risk adoption in the first two seasons. The DCE confirms that the per-hectare payment is the main accelerator of adoption; in practice, this may be delivered by a buyer premium on contracted hectares, potentially blended with a small public contribution to cover initial costs of certification and monitoring. In time, as practices normalise and monitoring costs fall, the public component can taper.

Policy and governance

The case leverages Bulgaria's experience with quality schemes and the institutional scaffolding around the wine sector, but it recognises that trust is earned through clarity and ease, not merely through regulation. Contracts should be short to medium term, with renewal options and minimal administrative burden. A neutral intermediary (cooperative, producer group or a recognised regional body) can reduce transaction costs, organise basic monitoring, and interface with buyers. Public agencies still matter: their role is to co-finance early fixed costs (e.g., advisory time, initial monitoring protocol, label registration) and to provide light-touch oversight so that claims remain credible without becoming onerous.

Organic vineyards in integrated production

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Netherlands

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

Rabo Carbon bank

Summarize

The Dutch Rabobank supports farmers in developing sustainable business models (e.g., by offering financing solutions and agronomic advice). These business models seek carbon reductions by switching towards regenerative farming practices. Practices include reductions in chemical fertilisers and pesticides, improvements in crop rotation, adding cover crops, and rising water levels. The carbon reduction achieved by these practices is verified, and carbon credits are sold.

The bank operates internationally. Three-year trials for the described 'Rabo Carbon Bank' currently run in the US and the Netherlands with dairy and arable farmers (Banken NL, 2022). The generated carbon credits are sold to large companies such as Vattenfall (Rabobank, 2022)

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Objectives

In the NOVASOIL Project, we will analyse factors relevant to Dutch farmers' acceptance of the business model. A discrete choice experiment (DCE) will be used to determine the influence of contract attributes (e.g., contract lengths, financial and agronomic support, prices on offer, and management requirements) and current farming practices. To identify relevant attributes for the experiment, cooperation with the relevant stakeholders (Dutch farmers, Rabobank) will be sought.

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

High agricultural commodity prices may encourage intensive farming practices

Potential enablers

Social awareness (interested in regenerative farming practices), policies, potential support for investments (e.g., in technologies)

Potential stakeholders

Rabobank and other financial service providers, farmers, farmers' associations, farmer collectives

Ecosystem services

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Latvia

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

Zemnieku saeima

Summarize

The goal of the Novasoil case-study is to ensure introduction of ZSA DIH a new digital solution – map services that provides the showcases of the fields in which farmers have implemented eco-schemes with soil friendly agricultural practices in Latvia. By displaying this information on a digital map, any person will be able to easily locate and learn about the farmers in their region who are actively working to improve soil health.

A digital map service containing information on Latvian soils can help farmers choose the right agrotechnical methods. By deploying the service in a production environment and implementing additional features, it can be tested during regular business operations. The Novasoil case study raises awareness of soil health and inspires farmers to adopt sustainable practices. The creation of a digital map highlighting organic fields is promoting sustainable agricultural growth in Latvia.

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

Economic downturn – In scope of declining income, farmers may refrain from eco-schemes in order to receive short-term economic benefits.

Bureaucracy – in face of too harsh requirements as well as very detailed application procedure, farmers may choose not to apply for certain eco-schemes.

Lack of know-how – Since many eco-schemes (precision agriculture for example) require additional knowledge, those farmers who lack it, may decide not to introduce eco-schemes.

Potential enablers

People's growing interest in sustainable land management can encourage the implementation of eco-schemes that benefit soil health. For farmers, prioritizing soil health can lead to long-term economic gains by maximizing yields and ensuring future profitability.

Potential stakeholders

Individual farmers, Farmers' NGOs, Policy makers, Environmental NGOs, Agricultural input suppliers, Agricultural machinery and technology providers, Individuals from society, Local authorities.

Data availability

Risks

The main risk is the accuracy and uptake of the digital service. If data are outdated or incomplete, farmer trust may be undermined. Similarly, if farmers or the public do not actively use the service, its impact on soil health awareness and practice adoption may be limited.

Business model and soil health perspective

The Latvian case study builds on the integration of soil data into a digital mapping service hosted within the ZSA Digital Innovation Hub (DIH). The solution highlights the fields where farmers have implemented eco-schemes and soil-friendly agricultural practices, thereby turning soil health improvements into visible, spatialised information. The service is practice-neutral, but it is grounded in the principles of sustainable management—reduced tillage, crop diversification, cover crops, and organic matter management—by making these actions transparent and comparable across regions.

The business model dimension relies on digitalisation: by lowering the transaction costs of eco-scheme participation and providing easy access to up-to-date data, the service creates value for farmers, policymakers, and the public. For farmers, it translates soil knowledge into actionable advice, helping them select agrotechnical methods best suited to local soil types and conditions.

Economic perspective

The mapping service does not provide direct payments to farmers but strengthens their capacity to comply with eco-scheme requirements and optimise land management. By aligning with statutory eco-scheme funding, it indirectly facilitates access to CAP support. Farmers benefit economically through:

- Reduced information costs (knowing which practices are relevant to their soils).
- Improved decision-making, leading to better soil fertility and resilience.
- Enhanced visibility, which can support market differentiation and reputational benefits.

Policy and governance

The ZSA DIH system operates within the policy context of the Latvian CAP Strategic Plan and the EU Soil Strategy 2030. Eco-schemes define the baseline of eligible practices, while the mapping tool provides an additional layer of transparency and communication. ZSA ensures that data integration and interface design meet both farmer needs and public expectations.

Universities and research institutions contribute to methodological robustness, for example by validating soil typology and mechanical composition data.

DIH System in Latvia

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

United Kingdom

novasoil

The NOVASOIL project aims to show the benefits for society and the environment of investing in soil health.

The main output of the project will be a tool to analyse the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health.

This tool will be based on best practice examples in Europe and other countries, as well as on the needs and demands of society.

Landscape Enterprise Networks Summarize

The University of Leeds' NOVASOIL project case study is the Landscape Enterprise Network (LENs). Developed by 3Keel - a sustainability consulting firm - LENs is an approach to developing integrated, place-based marketplaces for ecosystem functions. Adopted by Nestlé, Cargill, Affinity Water, Anglian Water and other stakeholders, LENs is a good example of a reliable and profitable business model that can promote soil health.

The basic concept underpinning LENs is co-procurement of ecosystem services from a collective of farmers/land managers, mediated via trusted supply and demand aggregators. This facilitates corporations and government agencies interested in incentivising nature-based solutions and realising landscape-level outcomes in establishing trading contracts with farmers, farmer cooperatives and landscape managers who can provide aggregated ecosystem services.

Figure 1. Structure of the NOVASOIL project

Objectives

In line with NOVASOIL project objectives, we will assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats associated with adopting LENs to:

- 1) incentivise adoption of land management practices by farmers/farmer cooperatives/land managers;
- 2) encourage corporations/government agencies to take a holistic, landscape-level perspective on soil health and commit to scaling up soil health-related outcomes.

Case studies properties

Potential inhibitors

Lack of long-term contracts, uncertainty due to changing UK policy and difficulty for partners to negotiate fair and accountable contracts.

Potential enablers

Formal and informal relationships, the existence of bodies representing farmers, awareness of the importance of soil health, the emergence of an agricultural carbon market in the UK and increasing pressure on businesses to contribute to the pathway towards net zero emissions by 2050.

Potential stakeholders

Cumbria LENs: Nestlé, United Utilities, First Milk, Eden Rivers Trust, Environment Agency, Eden District Council, and the National Trust
 East Anglia LENs: Affinity Water, Anglian Water, Cargill, Cereal Partners UK, Essex and Suffolk Water, Nestlé Purina, and West Northamptonshire County Council

Specific objectives

- SO1** Develop a multidimensional portfolio of business cases and best practices for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analyse existing global models and create new incentives and benefits from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development model for soil health modelling
- SO4** Develop prototypes and a test network for incentives.
- SO5** Analyse current policies and technologies related to soil health and farmers' incomes.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan.

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Estonia

novasoil

The aim of the NOVASOIL project is to demonstrate that investing in soil health delivers benefits for society and the environment. The main output of the project is a tool that allows analysis of different soil health investment opportunities across Europe. This tool is based on case studies in European and third countries that highlight both the uniqueness and the diversity of soil health investments.

Landscape Enterprise Networks

Summarize

The Agricultural Research Centre (METK) is Estonia's agricultural research and knowledge centre under the Ministry of Rural Affairs. METK develops and tests agricultural technologies, produces seeds, researches plant health, and develops agronomic and agro-technological solutions to improve soil health, plant productivity and quality. Based on soil research and monitoring, METK develops solutions to increase soil health and provides agricultural advisory services.

The described activities are related to improving soil health and sustainable farming practices, such as assessing soil organic matter content, conducting soil analyses, and modelling soil fertility using GIS-based methods. The aim is to ensure soil health knowledge transfer, to raise awareness, and to underline the importance of soil health in food production, while ensuring sustainability and high-quality plant production.

Figure 1. NOVASOIL project structure

Objectives

In line with the objectives of the NOVASOIL project, we assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to the introduction of LENs in order to:

1. encourage farmers/agricultural cooperatives/land managers to adopt soil management practices;
2. motivate corporations/governments to take a holistic, landscape-level perspective on soil health and to commit to improving soil health outcomes.

Case Study Description

Possible inhibitors

Agriculture faces economic, climatic and technological challenges, including high input costs, lack of support, shortage of skilled labour, climate change impacts, pests and IT risks. In addition, there are problems with the availability of skilled labour and IT security.

Potential enablers

The presence of official and non-official networks, organisations representing farmers, researchers and advisory services, as well as the increasing role of agricultural producers' organisations in the European Union and the growing awareness of the importance of soil health, all contribute to this. Moreover, the EU's long-term vision for rural areas, which extends to 2050, provides a supportive framework.

Possible stakeholders

Other institutions: METK; Ministry of Rural Affairs; Ministry of the Environment; Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech); Estonian University of Life Sciences; University of Tartu; Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce; NGOs; Scandagra; Baltic Agro; Estonia OU; Voore Farm OU; Agrone and interested producers.

Ecosystem services

Data availability

Risks

First, administrative load: small farms may find compliance and claims management onerous. SoilHub and advisory services can mitigate this by offering templates, digital workflows and help-desk functions that reduce the time cost of doing the right thing. Second, climate variability: rotations and cover crops must remain viable in dry or cold springs; agronomic menus should therefore include harder mixes and flexible establishment windows. Third, data fragmentation: if soil-map layers, farm records and agency systems don't talk to each other, transaction costs rise and trust erodes. The remedy is interoperability and light data standards so that evidence for MRV is portable across tools and programmes.

Preliminary results

Scaled across METK's network and adopters, the package should improve aggregate stability, reduce erosion risk on vulnerable textures, and maintain or build soil organic carbon through more frequent living cover and prudent nutrient management. Economically, it supports yield stability and the reputation premium associated with certified seed produced under verifiable soil-friendly systems. Strategically, Estonia demonstrates how a robust formal architecture can be turned into farmer-centred practice when (i) supports are predictable, (ii) MRV piggybacks on existing data, and (iii) a boundary organisation keeps institutions and farms aligned.

Economic perspective

On the income side, farms combine basic income support with the environment-friendly production package. These pillars de-risk rotations, cover and careful fertilisation, which in turn safeguard the quality and consistency required for certified seed markets. Where field infrastructure limits performance, melioration support finances essential works. Over time, marketing labels and digital transparency (map-based profiles of soil-friendly management) can yield a modest but real premium, particularly in B2B seed channels sensitive to provenance and stewardship

Policy and governance

Estonia's policy environment on soil health relies primarily on supportive incentives—subsidies, compensatory payments and some voluntary finance mechanisms—rather than strict command-and-control rules. This pragmatic, farm-centred approach exerts medium-to-high influence on soil strategies. The governance landscape is formally strong, with ministries, agencies, advisory services and research actors actively involved. However, administrative burdens create friction, particularly for smaller farms that struggle to meet policy requirements. A key innovation is SoilHub (2024), conceived as a boundary organisation to bridge policy, research and land users, helping to align formal ambitions with practical implementation.

Integrated production in Estonia

Specific objectives

- SO1** Multi-dimensional portfolio development of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond.
- SO2** Analysis of current models around the world for creating new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils.
- SO3** Apply a co-development approach to modelling that promotes soil health.
- SO4** Develop a prototype incentive toolbox and test network.
- SO5** Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and income provision for farmers.
- SO6** Developing a community of practice around investors and key soil health actors.
- SO7** Increase interest in soil health through a digital marketing strategy plan

 Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

novasoil
INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

Italy

2 Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the EU for funding, in the frame of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement GA 101091268. The document reflects only the author's view. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

